

Supplementary Appendix

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Supplement to: Stein KR, Krings JG et al. A strategy to reduce out-of-user-life utilization and waste of expired budesonide-formoterol pMDI inhalers in mild asthma

A strategy to reduce out-of-user-life utilization and waste of expired budesonide-formoterol pMDI inhalers in mild asthma

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1. Table S1. Calculated daily budesonide-formoterol utilization in 4 trials

Study	Number of participants randomized to as-needed budesonide-formoterol	Median daily inhaled glucocorticoid metered dose (200/6 µg)	Calculated median number of actuations per 90 days
SYGMA1	1,277	60.2 (95% CI = 53.7, 67.0)	27.1 (95% CI = 24.2 - 30.15)
SYGMA2	2,089	65.9 (95% CI = 60.9, 72.5)	29.7 (95% CI = 27.4 - 32.6)
PRACTICAL	437 (with electronic monitoring data for budesonide-formoterol from n=55)*	164.3 (IQR = 74.0 - 251.7)	73.9 (IQR = 33.3 - 113.3)
Novel START	220 (with electronic monitoring data for budesonide-formoterol from n=215)*	73 (IQR = 31 - 146)	32.9 (IQR = 14.0 - 65.7)

Table S1. Calculated Daily Budesonide-Formoterol Utilization in Included Trials. The mean daily inhaled glucocorticoid metered dose (200/6 µg) from electronic inhaler monitors was extracted from Table S6 in SYGMA1¹, Table S2 in SYGMA2², Table 2 in PRACTICAL³, and Table 2 in Novel START⁴. * The median daily inhaled glucocorticoid dose was divided by 200 µg to calculate the median number of inhalations taken per day (1 inhalation = 200 µg of budesonide). This value was then multiplied by 90 to determine the total number of actuations taken over a 90-day period.

In PRACTICAL³, electronic inhaler monitors were used for 55/437 participants randomized to as-needed budesonide-formoterol, and 215/220 in Novel START. The values were confirmed with Novel START and PRACTICAL study authors. SYGMA1 and SYGMA2 had electronic monitoring data for all participants randomized to budesonide-formoterol.

Abbreviations used: SYGMA1: Inhaled Combined Budesonide-Formoterol As-Needed in Mild Asthma; SYGMA2: As-Needed Budesonide-Formoterol Versus Maintenance Budesonide in Mild Asthma; PRACTICAL: Budesonide-Formoterol Reliever Therapy Versus Maintenance Budesonide Plus Terbutaline Reliever Therapy in Adults with Mild to Moderate Asthma; and Novel START Controlled Trial of Budesonide-Formoterol As-Needed for Mild Asthma; IQR: interquartile range; CI: Confidence Interval.

2. Table S2. User-life and inputted pricing of the most commonly prescribed reliever inhalers for adults with asthma in the United States

Medication	Company or manufacturer in US	Device Type	Dosage Strengths	Number of Actuations	Average Wholesale Price ⁽¹⁾	Manufacturer-recommended User-life
Albuterol	Teva Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd. (ProAir RespiClick)	DPI	108 mcg	200	\$81	13 months
	Teva Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd (ProAir Digihaler)	MDI/DPI	108 mcg	200	\$108	13 months
	3M Drug Delivery Systems (Proventil HFA)	pMDI	108 mcg	200	\$93	12 months
	GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) (Ventolin HFA)	MDI	108 mcg	60 / 200	\$27 / \$68	13 months
Levalbuterol	Sunovion Pharmaceuticals Inc. (Xopenex HFA)	pMDI	59 mcg	200	\$81	Same as shelf life ⁽²⁾
Budesonide-Formoterol	AstraZeneca LP (Symbicort)	pMDI	160 mcg / 4.5 mcg*	60 / 120	\$318/ \$468	3 months
	Mylan Pharmaceuticals Inc (Breyna)	pMDI	160 mcg / 4.5 mcg*	120	\$445 ⁽³⁾	3 months
	Prasco Laboratories Inc	pMDI	160 mcg / 4.5 mcg*	120	\$402 ⁽³⁾	3 months
Mometasone-Formoterol	Organon and Co. Pharmaceuticals (Dulera)	pMDI	100 mcg / 5 mcg*	60 / 120	\$278 / \$411	Same as shelf life
Albuterol-budesonide	AstraZeneca Dunkerque Production (Airsupra)	MDI	90 mcg / 80 mcg (2 inhalations per dose)	120	\$570	12 months

Table S2. User-life and inputted pricing of commonly prescribed reliever inhalers for adults with asthma in the United States. The imputed pricing (as of August 1, 2023) and the user-life information of as-needed inhalers along with the manufacturer, device type, dosage strengths, and number of actuations for each strength are listed for each inhaler.

Supplementary Appendix

*These doses of budesonide-formoterol are expressed as delivered doses, whereas in the published study reports doses of budesonide-formoterol are expressed as metered doses. A metered dose of 200/6 mcg budesonide-formoterol corresponds to a delivered dose of 160/4.5 mcg.

Abbreviations used: U.S. United States; HFA: hydrofluoroalkane; DPI: dry powder inhaler; pMDI: pressurized metered dose inhaler; pMDI: pressurized metered dose inhaler; g: grams; mcg: micrograms; AWP: Average Wholesale Price. (1) Pricing data listed, except for generic budesonide-formoterol, was taken from Merative Micromedex in August 15, 2023. (2) Shelf life refers to the duration of time during which the inhaler is reported to remain stable, effective, and safe for use while it remains in its packaging. Inhaler user-life refers to the time from inhaler unpackaging until the time the manufacturer no longer confirms medication potency and recommends disposal (3) Due to introduction of generic budesonide-formoterol after modeling, pricing data for generic budesonide-formoterol as of September 27, 2024 using same source.

3. Discrepancy in PRACTICAL and Novel START Budesonide-Formoterol Randomization Group

In the PRACTICAL study, only 55 out of 437 patients randomized to the budesonide-formoterol group (12.6%) had electronic inhaler monitoring. In Novel START, 215 out of 220 (97.7%) had electronic inhaler monitoring and had individualized data provided. In the other two studies (SYGMA1 and SYGMA2), all patients randomized to budesonide-formoterol had electronic monitoring of inhaler use. These differences (only a subset of PRACTICAL participants having electronic inhaler monitoring and only 215 of 220 participants having individualized data provided by authors for Novel START) explain the difference between the total number of patients randomized to budesonide-formoterol and the number of patients with electronic monitoring reported in the Results section. The total of 3,636 patients reflects only those with electronic monitoring data.

4. Statistical Methods for PRACTICAL and Novel START Violin Plots

The Boxplot method was used to produce a ‘Schematic’ Boxplot. This boxplot includes a symbol for the mean, while the central, upper, and lower lines of the box represent the median, 75th quantile, and 25th quantile, respectively. The whiskers extend to the maximum and minimum observations above and below the upper and lower ‘Fences,’ which are defined as 1.5 times the IQR above the 75th or below the 25th percentiles. Outliers are individual observations that fall outside these fences. The output from Proc Boxplot was provided by the PRACTICAL and Novel START authors and was used to generate the boxplots.

The Kernel Density Estimation was performed using the default settings in SAS, specifically with Proc KDE and the ‘Sheather-Jones’ plug-in method, to estimate probability densities based on a scoring dataset. The scoring dataset and kernel density estimations were provided to the team as a spreadsheet.

The Violin plots were then generated using Proc Sgplot, incorporating a ‘Vbox’ statement for the boxplot, a ‘Series’ statement for the lines showing the kernel density estimations, and a ‘Band’ statement to fill the violin plot. SAS version 9.4 was used.

4.1 PRACTICAL Data Set

4.1a Data Description for ‘Schematic’ Style Boxplot

Data descriptor for ICS actuations per 90 days	
N	55
MIN	3.025
Q1	33.277
MEAN	79.193
MEDIAN	73.911
Q3	113.25
MAX	307.103
STDDEV	64.368
HIWHISKR	213.118
HIGH	240
HIGH	307.103

4.1b Frequency of Actuations Below Limits

ICS actuations per 90 days	N/55 (%)
Less than or equal to 60	26 (47.3)
Less than or equal to 120	44 (80)

4.2 Novel START Data Set

4.2a Data Description for ‘Schematic’ Style Plot

Data descriptor for ICS actuations per 90 days	
N	215
MIN	0
Q1	15.587
MEAN	49.154
MEDIAN	34.286
Q3	67.437
MAX	355.61
STDDEV	49.004
HIWHISKR	132.938
HIGH	152.017
HIGH	153.127
HIGH	167.625
HIGH	170.217
HIGH	187.297
HIGH	208.659
HIGH	212.143
FARHIGH	224.622
FARHIGH	226.098
FARHIGH	355.61

4.2b Frequency of Actuations Below Limits

ICS actuations per 90 days	N/215 (%)
Less than or equal to 60	154 (71.6)
Less than or equal to 120	201 (93.5%)

5. Monte Carlo Modeling

A probabilistic decision model was constructed to evaluate the cost effectiveness of 60-actuation budesonide-formoterol inhalers versus 120-actuation inhalers over a 90-day time horizon. Model inputs included a daily actuation random variable and constant cost per actuation variables for the 60- and 120-actuation inhalers. To construct the daily actuation random variable, normally distributed vectors were generated using observation counts and daily actuation parameters from four clinical trials: SYGMA-1, SYGMA-2, PRACTICAL, and Novel START. These vectors were joined to generate a normal meta-distribution. Mean and standard deviation parameters from the meta distribution were computed and converted to shape and scale parameters, as the random variable was modelled with a gamma distribution in the decision model. The daily actuation variable was used to generate 90-day actuation values and multiplied by the cost per actuation values defined for each inhaler type. Merative Micromedex[®] was used to determine the average wholesale price for each inhaler type and average cost per actuation values were computed. The decision model was evaluated probabilistically by sampling variables from their uncertainty distributions. Model evaluation entailed 100,000 replicates to ensure generation of a fully saturated empirical actuation and cost distribution.

6. Supplementary References

1. O'Byrne PM, FitzGerald JM, Bateman ED, Barnes PJ, Zhong N, Keen C, et al. Inhaled Combined Budesonide–Formoterol as Needed in Mild Asthma. *N Engl J Med*. 2018;378(20):1865–76.
2. Bateman ED, Reddel HK, O'Byrne PM, Barnes PJ, Zhong N, Keen C, et al. As-Needed Budesonide–Formoterol versus Maintenance Budesonide in Mild Asthma. *N Engl J Med*. 2018;378(20):1877–87.
3. Hardy J, Baggott C, Fingleton J, Reddel HK, Hancox RJ, Harwood M, et al. Budesonide-formoterol reliever therapy versus maintenance budesonide plus terbutaline reliever therapy in adults with mild to moderate asthma (PRACTICAL): a 52-week, open-label, multicentre, superiority, randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2019;394(10202):919–28.
4. Beasley R, Holliday M, Reddel HK, Braithwaite I, Ebmeier S, Hancox RJ, et al. Controlled Trial of Budesonide–Formoterol as Needed for Mild Asthma. *N Engl J Med*. 2019;380(21):2020–30.